

Exposure From Learning Activities, Beliefs, Motivation, And Learning Resources To English Language Acquisition: What Mothers Think?

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Abstract: The process of how children acquire a language has been a complex one to uncover. Recently, several studies have been examining the role of mothers in this process. Mothers are viewed to function as a vital part of the children's language input and nurturing their interest in language learning. This study examines the maternal perspectives in support of raising learners' awareness towards the importance of daily exposure to the English language while using various methods, which contribute to learning a second language. The research used multiple regression analysis to determine whether exposure from learning activities, beliefs, motivation, and learning resources to the English language predicts language acquisition. Using G power, the recommended sample size of the study was 129. Using convenient sampling, the researcher gathered data from one hundred twenty-nine ($n = 129$) respondents through a survey questionnaire. In this study, it was revealed that mothers' perceptions of the exposure of learning resources, beliefs, learning activities, and motivation to English language acquisition show high positive correlations. Also, it was found out in the multiple regression analysis that the exposure to learning resources, activities, and motivation was a significant predictor of English language acquisition.

Keywords: Impact of Exposure, Maternal Perspective, Language Acquisition, English

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of the English language cannot be overstated in an escalating globalized world, as the question of when to begin learning English follows the requirement to do so. According to Naja Ferjan Ramirez, a research scientist at the University of Washington, learning English earlier is significantly more effective in terms of brain function (Mitchell, 2017). Similar to this, Language Trainers concluded that it is now more important than ever for parents to give their children the opportunity to learn languages so that they can develop lifelong skills (The Importance of Early Exposure to Language, 2014). Undoubtedly, parents are the primary language models in introducing and strengthening language in young children. Such a fact has not gone unnoticed as Hazlegreaves (2019) consequently explains that the effect of encouraging language, starting as early as when the child is in the womb, is a vital element of human development. In this study, the maternal perspective is given a spotlight on language development for inquiry in view of mothers spending more time with their children than anyone else, and they are often motivated to help their children learn

English, which implies that mothers are more involved in their children's linguistic growth. Research data reveals that there is a diversity of opinion among mothers regarding the ideal method for children to learn English as presented in studies that children who are exposed to English at an early age tend to acquire the language more easily and quickly than children who begin learning English later in life (Halle et al., 2012; Mitchel, 2017; Muñoz & Cadierno, 2021; Qureshi, 2022). Remarkably, this point was also collated from various research by Newport (1990) on acquiring first and second languages, that proper language learning only happens when exposure to the language starts early in life. Then, the effect of exposure to the English language on language learning has been the subject of several studies. The existing research sought to ascertain how exposure to English impacts language development, as claimed to help in language learning (Hu, 2016; Newport, 1990). On the contrary, only one study specifically investigates the maternal perspective wherein Sorenson Duncan, T., & Paradis, J. (2018) suggest that greater maternal education is linked to more enriched language input for children, which can positively impact language acquisition. There is, however, little data, according to Lan et al. (2013), concerning whether or not mothers consider themselves to be "teachers" of English and literacy. Considering this, point in fact, acknowledging the maternal perspective in the accumulated data will complement to the effective language input to children reviving the maternal role in the guidance of providing quality as a response to the research conducted by Zoubi (2018) supporting his recommendation on raising learners' awareness towards the importance of learning English language through exposure. Pursuing this further based on maternal responses, this study aimed to determine whether exposure from learning activities, beliefs, motivation, and learning resources predicts English language acquisition.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this inferential study, the exposure from learning activities, beliefs, motivation, and learning resources to English language acquisition was examined, and which independent variables that are significant predictors of English language acquisition were identified. Using G-power, as developed by Faul et al. (2007), the sample size was determined, which consists of 129 participants between 18-65 years of age who are Filipino mothers. The sample group was formed using convenience sampling. A 5-point Likert scale type by Al Zoubi (2018) was utilized due to its applicability to the present study, offering five responses ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree". Divided into two sections, the questionnaire began with the first part highlighting the impact of exposure to the English language on language acquisition, with ten items, including Learning Activities, Beliefs, Motivation, and Learning Resources. While the second section focused on the impact of exposure to the English language on the development of the four language skills, with nine items. Also, information related to the participants' age, education levels, marital status, residence, occupation, language background, and family language policy was obtained using the demographic information of the participants. The results of the "Multiple Regression Analysis" are presented in Table 3, as it is a statistical technique that will help us to identify if the variables are significant predictors of language acquisition, as well as the significant independent variable in the study (Cho & Awbi, 2007). All the variables were analyzed for Filipino mothers. The study is both anonymous and voluntary, and the information gathered will only be used for research purposes. The significance value in the study was accepted as $p < .05$. The obtained data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the study, the dependent variable is language acquisition, and the independent variables are learning activities, beliefs, motivation, and learning resources. Multiple Regression Analysis was conducted. The descriptive statistics of variables for mothers are shown in Table 1. Scale scores were computed by getting the mean score in each scale, resulting in a minimum possible score of 1 and a maximum of 5. The mean score for language acquisition was 4.056 (SD=1.511), the mean score for learning activities was 4.372 (SD=1.233), the mean score for beliefs was 4.233 (SD=1.174), the mean score for motivation was 4.341 (SD=1.241), and the mean score for learning resources was 3.828 (SD=1.316).

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N= 129	
	Mean	Std. Deviation
Language Acquisition	4.056	1.151
Learning Activities	4.372	1.233
Beliefs	4.233	1.174
Motivation	4.341	1.241
Learning Resources	3.828	1.316

In order to conduct Regression analysis, the relationship between variables was examined in the study. The results are given in Table 2. As seen in the table, it was found that there is a positive significant correlation between language acquisition and learning activities ($r=.772$), beliefs ($r=.688$); motivation ($r=.733$); learning resources ($r=.981$). There is a positive significant correlation between learning activities and beliefs ($r=.940$); motivation ($r=.948$); learning resources ($r=.711$). There is a positive significant correlation between beliefs and motivation ($r=.967$); learning resources ($r=.646$). There is a positive significant correlation between motivation and learning resources ($r=.701$). All variables have positive significant correlations, which indicate that the variables are all positively correlated to each other at $p<0.001$.

Table 2 Correlation Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Language Acquisition	1.000				
2. Learning Activities	.772	1.000			
3. Beliefs	.688	.940	1.000		
4. Motivation	.733	.948	.967	1.000	
5. Learning Resources	.981	.711	.646	.701	1.000

* $p<0.05$

The results of the Multiple Regression Analysis conducted revealed that learning resources, learning activities, and motivation are significant predictors ($R=.989$, $R^2=.978$, $F_{(3,125)} = 1835.84$, $p<.05$), with an R^2 of .989. When the t values related to the significance of regression coefficients are examined, only learning resources, learning activities, and motivation variables are the biggest contributors, respectively. According to the findings, mothers perceive those children exposed to learning resources, learning activities, and motivation are likely to have a significant impact on language acquisition. As a result, as seen in Table 3, the model explains that only learning resources, learning activities, and motivation are significant predictors of English language acquisition.

Table 3 Multiple Regression Analysis Results of the Predictor Variables of English Language Acquisition

Model	B	Std. Error	β	t	F	R	R^2	R^2 Change
(1 st Step)								
(Constant)	.774	.062		12.577	3174.593			
Learning Resources	.857	.015	.981	56.344		.981	.962	.961
(2 nd Step)								
(Constant)	.517	.063		8.226				
Learning Resources	.763	.018	.873	41.828	2258.961			
Learning Activities	.141	.019	.151	7.255		.986	.973	.972
(3 rd Step)								

(Constant)	.548	.057		9.544				
Learning Resources	.774	.017	.885	46.365				
Learning Activities	.329	.040	.353	8.279	1835.835	.989	.978	.977
Motivation	-.206	.039	-.222	-5.275				

In final analysis, findings obtained from the study show that exposure from learning resources, activities, and motivation were significant predictors of English language acquisition. Children, in general, encounter the English language frequently throughout their daily lives, which supports the benefit of learning the language in its natural environment. The findings in also indicated high positive correlations from exposure on learning resources, learning activities, motivation, beliefs on English language acquisition. Researchers likewise suggest that children attain the acquired language when exposed to it even from an early age and are more likely to become proficient in that language than those who are not exposed to English language until later in life. The amount and quality of language exposure have a significant impact on language acquisition, according to a research study on bilingual kids. Point in fact, language proficiency, in the study of Ito and Sakai (2021), is predicted by people's exposure to language during both early and late learning stages. Prior research continues to be evident as reported by Clayden et al. (2023) that exposure to dominant target language in class and supporting environments outside of the classroom are important predictors of cognition in childhood. In addition, learners who receive a lot of it at different levels are more receptive to language learning. The growth of the four language skills and exposure to the English language are also strongly correlated. Mothers further perceive that there is certainty on the development of necessary English language acquisition but children who are exposed less are less likely to do so. According to studies, these aspects of language acquisition, along with other individual differences and learning environments, are important (BEDORE et al., 2016; Bello et al., 2023; Ito & Sakai, 2021; Vermeij et al., 2022; Zoubi, 2018). Finally, even though there were no specific studies that disputed the effect of exposure to the English language on language acquisition, it is crucial to keep in mind that language learning is a complex process that is influenced by a variety of elements, including aptitude, cognitive ability, and educational approaches. Research supports the assertion made by authors like Choi et al. (2020), Duncan & Paradis (2018), Hammer et al. (2009), Hoff et al. (2018), and Luo et al. (2021) that bilingual children's exposure to and acquisition of the English language are significantly influenced by their mothers' beliefs, education, and language practices including maternal education, lifestyle choices, and beliefs. All these potential aspects could influence the linguistic environment in a way that also affects how children develop their attitudes and language skills.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, maternal perspective is given a spotlight on language development for inquiry in view of mothers spending more time with their children than anyone else and they are often motivated to help their children learn English which implies that mothers are more involved in their children's language acquisition. Effects of exposure to the English language on language acquisition has been given focus of interest in numerous studies, which have also been reported by Dako & Quarcoo (2017) that English has already invaded the language of the home. This study supplements the sparse literature on the specific contributing aspect of maternal perspective on different early literacy skills reviving the maternal role of providing quality of exposure and in promoting awareness to complement the study of Zoubi (2018) towards the importance of learning English language through exposure. In this study, it was revealed that mothers' perceptions on the exposure of learning resources, belief, learning activities, and motivation to English language acquisition show high positive correlations. Having more exposure to English language develops proficiency in the four language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing). Also, it was found out in the multiple regression analysis that the exposure from learning resources, learning activities, and motivation were significant predictors of English language acquisition. In light of the obtained key information, mothers affirm the notion that more exposure to English language develops acquisition through learning resources, which provide opportunities to see and hear the target language in a variety of contexts such as watching English TV programmes, videos, or movies, watching a lot of English TV programmes, videos, or movies without subtitles in one's own language, using social media (Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, etc...), and surfing the internet helps in learning English language. Also, learning activities, provide

opportunities for learners to practice using the target language in a meaningful way, such as practicing English language outside the classroom, doing English homework and project work, and using English in real life situations increase English fluency. In addition, mothers perceive that motivation also predicts English language acquisition as they get to encourage children to speak English even when mistakes are also possible as children are likely to develop the English language acquisition when inculcated with a desire to learn a new language.

Interestingly, the study is directly aligned with the Input Hypothesis of Stephen Krashen, a notable theorist at work, who was reported by Shameem (n.d.) for establishing a general theory of second language acquisition, as the cofounder of the Natural Approach, and as the inventor of sheltered subject matter teaching. Affirming that frequency and quality of exposure play a significant role in predicting and developing language skills, individuals are more likely to develop English language acquisition the more exposure they receive it. Consequently, the researchers propose the three pillars of language acquisition: learning resources, learning activities, and motivation mark a promising approach in creating a supportive environment for language acquisition. When granted access to the appropriate resources, engagement in meaningful activities, and are motivated to learn, children are perceived to develop English language acquisition. Furthermore, with the established data, access is possible through the conscious efforts of parents, teachers, and other stakeholders in the field of language learning. In future research, paternal views could also be considered for any similarities or differences from the maternal perspective and how could the three pillars of language acquisition: learning resources, learning activities, and motivation be used to improve acquisition interventions. In doing so, existing literature will be enriched.

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